

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF LOCAL BUDGETS IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGION

Olimov Shohijahon Fozilxon ugli

Namangan state university, Faculty of economics

The direction of the economy 3-stage student.

Abstract. This scientific article explains the role of the local budget in the development of the region and comments on its importance.

Key words: budget, economic reform, tax, social life, governing body.

Sign in . In the period of deepening of social and economic reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in all spheres of our social life, implementation of deep changes in the sphere of finance and budget is the main demand of the present day.

As Uzbekistan sets itself the task of building a democratic state, the formation of the state budget plays an important role in this. At the time when market relations are gradually forming and developing in the economy, the need to have centralized financial resources for the performance of permanent tasks of the state is increasing.

An important structural part of the democratic state structure is the local state administrative bodies and their activities . In order to fulfill the tasks assigned to them , the local state control bodies must have certain property and financial-budgetary rights . Local authorities , governors , councils of people's deputies carry out state financial activities within their powers .

The main part. The local budget is considered to be the main structural part of the financial system of territorial state administrative bodies .

In accordance with Article 2 of the Law " On Local State Authorities " , the financial resources of the province , district , city, budget funds , extra - budgetary funds, credit resources , as well as the Republic (region, Tashkent city) constitute subsidies and subsidies allocated from the budget "

Through local budgets, public education, healthcare, cultural and sports institutions, local self-governing bodies, and allowances for low-income families are financed. At the same time, local budgets are the main support of the state's policy of social protection of the population. Almost 100% of the costs of social protection of the population are financed by local budgets.

The main function of the budget is to redistribute the national income to create material conditions for the existence of the state, to ensure production relations and reproduction. Local budgets are an important component of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and are a financial source for the activities of local authorities. The system of local budgets makes it possible to fully satisfy local needs and to implement the measures implemented by the state in a centralized manner . Local authorities are tasked with the increase of local budget revenues and efficient use of resources . The growth rate of economy and culture is directly related to the mobilization of local economic resources, the organization of work on the economical use of funds, which in turn It helps in ensuring the implementation of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Social and economic development of local areas is provided with financial resources through local budgets.

IAKarimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, emphasized this direction in the formation of local budget revenues: "It is necessary to give a large part of the state budget revenues to localities, to strengthen local budgets. This allows to increase the independence of regions, increase their initiative, interest in the implementation of the budget and their responsibility in this regard. In addition, it encourages local budgets to find new sources of revenue, strengthens local budget discipline" [1]

The deepening of reforms in Uzbekistan requires local authorities to further increase their role in the socio-economic development of regions, expand their rights in the field of finance and budget, and strengthen their financial base. The increase

in local budgets is mainly due to the increase in expenses . That is, the state is transferring the economy, social infrastructure, labor force training costs to the localities, the local budgets are widely used to influence the state reproduction process, the local management is in accordance with the purpose of the state in the localities . b fulfills his duties i .

The local budgets of the Republic of Uzbekistan must have revenues to cover expenses. Therefore, if we analyze the current state of formation of local budget revenues and the sources of revenue in this process, first of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of revenues. Sources of local budget revenues include local taxes and levies, deductions from state taxes, subsidies, subsidies, loans, funds transferred to state property by inheritance, donation, physical, legal and non-returnable funds from foreign countries. , includes income from the placement and use of state property, as well as other income.

1 - drawing

Local budget revenues

Sources[2]

is carried out in accordance with Article 18 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan " Budget System " . Accordingly, local budget revenues are formed from their own income (local taxes and levies) and allocations from the higher budget (deductions from state taxes, grants and subsidies) .

2 - drawing

The structure of the tax system in Uzbekistan today [3]

State taxes	Local taxes and fees
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tax in favor of legal entities. 2. Personal income tax. 3. VAT 4. Excise tax 5. Land use tax _ _ _ 6. micro-firms and small enterprises , as well as trade and catering enterprises 7. Customs fees 8. Single customs fee when individuals bring goods from abroad 9. State duty 10. Other income 	<p><i>Own taxes :</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Property tax 2. Land tax 3. Uniform land tax 4. Landscaping and social infrastructure development tax _ 5. Consumption tax for the use of gasoline, diesel fuel and liquefied gas in vehicles 6. License fee for the sale of certain types of goods and the provision of certain types of services 7. Registration fee for legal entities and individuals. <p>Taxes paid in full . _ _</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use of water resources tax for _ 2. A fixed tax of individuals engaged in business without establishing a legal entity 3. Excise duty on certain goods (plant k either)

The share of deductions from state taxes is changed every year depending on the income of local budgets and the amount of their expenses.

An important feature of national taxes is that the taxes that fall to the republican budget can be used as allocations for managing local budgets. If next year local budgets' sources of income (taxes) will increase, there will be no need to give deductions from republican taxes. Republican and local taxes have a single essence and are payments to be paid to the budget.

At the same time, some types of state taxes can be left at the disposal of local budgets as a source of supplementing local budgets . In particular, according to paragraph 14 of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 490 of December 31, 2001, in order to increase the responsibility and accountability of local authorities and management bodies for the full collection of revenues to the relevant budgets and the timely financing of approved expenses revenues from state taxes were transferred in full to the income of local budgets.

This type of income of local budgets has its own aspects.

Subsidies and grants allocated from higher budgets are different from other types of income Therefore , these types of income are received in the amount of the plan approved at the beginning of the year. That is, these types of income will not be changed during the year .

Conclusion . The ongoing economic reforms in the republic's economy make taxes an important tool for ensuring economic stability, and their continuous reform . q requires to be carried . Today, the majority of the population's income is formed in the private sector . The state has limited opportunities to manage these revenues , administratively diverting these revenues to state expenses is contrary to the principles of the market economy. It is possible to attract public income to budget revenues only through taxes .

In many foreign countries, the formation of local budget revenues is subject to strict rules in each case .

They must follow the principles established by law on the creation of regional budgets. The main ones are the principles of budget over-balance and budget stability . In other words, all the intended income and expenses should be reflected in this project .

Local taxes and fees are divided into 2 groups according to the method of determination :

1. Local taxes and fees introduced by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan ;
2. Local taxes and fees imposed at the discretion of local authorities .

According to Article 7 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the property and land tax is introduced by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is valid in all regions of Uzbekistan.

Local taxes and other types of fees are imposed by local authorities.

Determination of the rates of local taxes and the benefits granted according to them is at the discretion of the local authorities in accordance with the legal documents. In the formation of revenues of local budgets, the granting of such a right to local authorities on local taxes and fees plays an important role in the economy of the region. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added. The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.

References:

1. IAKarimov "Uzbekistan on the path of deepening economic reforms" T. "Uzbekistan" 1995. 204 b
2. Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). Fundamentals of education quality in higher education. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01),

149-151.

3. TOLIBJONOVICH, M. T., & OGLI, G. O. R. (2020). Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today. *JournalNX*, 6(10), 109-111.
4. Irgasheva, N., & Madaminov, K. F. N. (2020). DEVELOPING STUDENTS'MUSICAL CULTURE AND UNDERSTANDING BY LISTENING TO MUSIC. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8.
5. Madaminovich, F. Q. (2023). MUSICAL BROCHURE CREATED IN THE XI-XIII CENTURIES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(06), 192-195.
6. Madaminovich, F. Q. (2023). CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDIGENOUS MUSIC. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(06), 184-187.
7. Tillakhujayev, O. (2022). THE SCIENCE OF MUSIC AND THE ROLE OF KNOWLEDGE OF MUSIC LYRICS IN THE FORMATION OF THE MUSICAL CULTURE OF YOUNG PEOPLE. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 175-178.
8. Tillaxo'Jayev, O. (2022). OZARBAYJON MUMTOZ MUSIQASI ORQALI O'QUVCHILARDA BAYNALMINALLIK FAZILATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(4), 501-503.
- Tillahujayev, O. T. (2023). VOKAL SAN'ATIDA PROFESSIONAL IJROGA ERISHISHDA OVOZ IMKONIYATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH TEXNIKASI. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 4(1), 613-621.